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Data management plan (DMP)

**Steady-State Off-Design
Performance of a Double Spool
Turbofan Engine Using SIMULINK**

ICFD12-EG-5044

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	08/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project
2.0	21/11/2025	Update the contributors, Storage and backup

Level of distribution		<p>This DMP is licensed under a <u>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License</u> (CC BY 4.0).</p> <p>It is publicly available under 10.5281/zenodo.17703176</p>
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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
NASA	National Aeronautics And Space Administration
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection:
https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Experiment Results Data	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Experiment Results Data":

After conducting the experiment according to the software capability, the experiment results are exported in two configurations, the first which is this data set are the results tables for variation of fan and compressor parameters like pressure ratio and efficiency with the specific thrust or specific fuel consumption. The second configuration is plotting these data as figures and plots.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Fan and compressor maps	NASA TN-D-6653		no
R2	International Standard Atmosphere ISA	MATLAB/SIMULINK software under license of Mathworks		no

Description for "Fan and compressor maps":

1st Data set extracted from NASA repository (NASA TN -D-6553) by Laurence H. Fishbach and Robert W, Koenig "A Program for calculating design and off design performance of two and three spool turbofans with as many as three nozzle", 1972

Description for "International Standard Atmosphere ISA":

2nd Data Set extracted from International Standard Atmosphere "ISA" in Matlab/Simulink data library for the international standard atmosphere conditions (temperature and pressure) varied with the altitude.

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data consists of both reused and newly generated datasets. The reused dataset (for example, Fan and Axial Compressor maps) were obtained from external NASA engine performance data and manipulated through design conditions then imported into SIMULINK® for further usage and

analysis. The produced dataset (tables_final_18-7-2016.xlsx / datatables.csv) was generated from SIMULINK® simulations of the double-spool turbofan engine under off-design operating conditions. Data processing and organization were performed using MATLAB and Microsoft Excel to extract relevant performance parameters, create tables, and ensure machine-actionable formats suitable for further analysis.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The data will be structured according to the project's directory convention, including folders for input data, model files, simulation results, and analysis outputs. Filenames will follow a consistent naming pattern with timestamps and descriptive identifiers. Version control is maintained through GitHub to ensure that all updates to the Simulink model and related scripts are automatically tracked. Each dataset version is linked to the corresponding simulation run, enabling full traceability of results.

Metadata accompanying the project will provide essential descriptive information to allow the identification, understanding, and potential reuse of the data. Each dataset will include basic administrative details such as the project title, authors name, institutional affiliation (TU Wien), and date of data creation. Reference to the associated conference paper will also be included to link the data with its scientific context. Technical metadata will describe the software environment used to generate the results, including MATLAB/Simulink version numbers and any relevant toolboxes. The main file types (.slx, .mat, .m, .csv, and .png) will be identified, along with short explanations of key variables, for example thrust [N] and mass flow rate [kg/s]. While most parameter information is embedded in the Simulink model, additional notes are provided in a short readme file to clarify input assumptions and the operating conditions used in each simulation run. Structural metadata will briefly describe the directory organization of the preserved folder, distinguishing between input data, model files, and generated results. File names include timestamps to reflect versioning, methodological metadata describe the turbofan configuration, solver type, and main modeling assumptions

however, documentation of all intermediate processing steps is limited. To support discoverability, a short abstract and relevant keywords (e.g., turbofan engine, off-design, Simulink, gas turbine performance) will be attached to the dataset. Future extensions may include richer metadata standards and persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) to improve long-term reusability and citation. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

All documentation is stored together with the model and datasets in the project's GitHub repository. Each update to the Simulink model, input files, and analysis scripts includes commit messages describing the purpose of changes. A concise readme file outlines the folder structure, simulation procedure, and software requirements to reproduce the results. Users with MATLAB/Simulink can reuse the data by following the provided instructions. Future updates may add structured metadata templates and workflow descriptions to further support reproducibility.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: Consistency and quality were ensured by comparing simulation outputs with published reference results, either visually (side-by-side plots) or by extracting reference data for overlay plots. All model updates were tracked using GitHub version control to maintain traceability of changes..

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Bassam Elsayed Saleh Abrisha (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (Experiment Results Data), R1 (Fan and compressor maps), R2 (International Standard Atmosphere ISA) will be stored on TU servers like repositUm or TUGitLab which is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Me, the main investigator and the supervisors

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2018-01-08	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository

description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The NASA TN-D6653 scaled data and the simulation results are provided as CSV files and can be accessed with standard spreadsheet software or programming environments, while the ISA inlet conditions are part of the Simulink model and require MATLAB/Simulink to be reused.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	The target audience for these datasets includes aerospace engineers and researchers, academic instructors and students, and developers of simulation or modeling tools.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The Principal Investigator, *Bassam Elsayed Saleh Abrisha*, will be responsible for directing and coordinating the research data management process, including metadata creation, dataset organization, version control, documentation, and preparation of data for publication. As this is an individual research project, no research assistants are involved in day-to-day RDM activities. Supervisors provide scientific guidance but are not responsible for data management tasks. TU.it provides the institutional storage infrastructure but does not participate in project-level data management.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.